

The Absorbtion Process Of Public Aspirations In Regional Development Planning Of Gorontalo District

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 09, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 10, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Absorption, Planning, Aspiration Development, Community, Public Administration.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5773140</p>	<p><i>The purpose of this study is to describe and analyze the process of absorbing community aspirations in regional development planning. In the local perspective, the public administration. Methodology uses descriptive qualitative. The results showed that the Regional Development Planning Agency's Ability Level in absorbing community aspirations which was carried out technically, analytically, administratively and in communication had been implemented by Regional Development and Development Agency in the development planning process, only to ensure that community aspirations were well accommodated in the local government work plan. shrouded in a number of problems. Therefore, Regional Development and Development Agency's technical, analytical, administrative, and communication capabilities are not guaranteed to influence the aspirations of the community if this capacity is not supported by political capacity.</i></p>

Introduction

Community aspirations are a representation of development planning that should have a large place in the development plan so that good management is needed so that aspirations can be absorbed, for this the capacity of the Regional Development Planning Agency is very important in managing and bridging community aspirations so that they can be accommodated in development plans. As an agency responsible for regional development planning for the Gorontalo District Regional Development and Development Agency District, until now it is still faced with a number of problems, namely the low compatibility between community aspirations and the quality of the plans produced, this problem occurs as a result of the weak management function of Regional Development and Development Agency in managing aspiration data in the planning process. have not been able to adopt the various aspirations and needs of society properly.

The implementation of coordination carried out by Regional Development and Development Agency in realizing the aspirations of the community has been emphasized a lot in various kinds of regulations, including through the Minister of Home Affairs regulation number 6 of 2017 which demands that Regional Development and Development Agency, through its management capabilities, be able to coordinate various different elements that come from various groups and individuals. to produce a uniform and harmonious action on regional development targets. The problem found in this study is the weakness of the coordination function in the regional development planning mechanism so that the development that has occurred does not reflect the aspirations of the community.

Based on the results of the researchers' preliminary observations, that the ability of the apparatus possessed is more of a trigger for the management of aspirations which has not been going well, not all apartments have the ability to identify and solve regional development planning problems, especially in the aspirations of the community, while the readiness of Regional Development and Development Agency officials is very important to provide satisfaction. service to the community, (Saleh et al., 2013) 1 emphasizes that one of the indicators that can be used to see the quality of services provided by the government is participation, that the provision of public services must be able to encourage the emergence of positive community participation in the delivery of public services. pay attention to the aspirations, needs and expectations of the wider community.

At present, Gorontalo District Regional Development and Development Agency still relies on human resources as planners to drive the implementation of development planning. However, in moving the planning, it does not only rely on technically capable planners and methods, but must be supported by other capabilities. The planning apparatus assigned by Regional Development and Development Agency is technically very familiar with work procedures to carry out their work, but in terms of supporting capabilities such as the ability to facilitate, review, correct, and provide input to aspirations that come from the community, these criteria are

not yet owned by Regional Development and Development Agency, a lot of work is done by the apparatus. Regional Development and Development Agency is only fulfilling their duties and interests which in the end has not been able to have a big influence on the aspirations of the community.

So far, it feels that the activities carried out by Regional Development and Development Agency have not been able to move the community to be able to actively participate, the problem of community participation that does not go well starts from communication, with the communication carried out it can increase aspirations because the messages given contain development ideas can stimulate the community to be more active in participation. (Saleh et al., 2013) 2 emphasize that as officials who are at the forefront of public services, ideally they must have oral communication skills because they are the ones who interact a lot with stakeholders so that the impression of good and bad service quality lies in the ability to communicate orally. The main duties of the apparatus in development communication include conveying information to the public about development,

Formulation of the problem

Based on the background that has been stated above, the formulation of the problem in this study is as follows: 1) What is the Ability Level of the Regional Development Planning Agency in Absorbing community aspirations in Gorontalo District, 2) How is the process of absorbing community aspirations in Regional Development Planning in Gorontalo District, 3). What factors inhibit and support the ability of the Regional Development Planning Agency to Absorb Community Aspirations in Gorontalo District, 4) What are the aspirations that can be accommodated and cannot be accommodated by the Regional Development Planning Agency in Gorontalo District, 5) What is the model of aspiration absorption community in regional development planning in Gorontalo District.

Research purposes

Based on the formulation of the problems that have been stated, the objectives of this study are as follows; 1). Describing & Analyzing the Ability of Regional Development Planning Agencies to Absorb Community Aspirations in Gorontalo District, 2). Describe & analyze the process of absorption of community aspirations in regional development planning in Gorontalo District, 3) Describe & analyze the inhibiting and supporting factors of the ability of regional development planning agencies to absorb community aspirations in Gorontalo District, 4) Describe aspirations that can be accommodated and cannot be accommodated. accommodated by the Regional Development Planning Agency in Gorontalo District, 5) Finding a model for the absorption of community aspirations in regional development planning in Gorontalo District.

Based on the theoretical study and description above, the framework of this research is as shown below.

Figure 1. Design Mindset

Benefits of research

The results of this study are expected to provide theoretical, constructive and academic benefits, as a material for knowledge and experience for researchers in compiling scientific works, as well as contributing ideas in the field of regional development planning for the development of science. In addition, as input for local governments who are interested in regional development planning issues.

RESEARCH METHODS

Qualitative research requires the determination of boundaries in research on the basis of the focus that arises as problems in research. In order to avoid research from data that is not relevant to the problem and the research objectives and objectives, as well as to limit the discussion of the problem from being widened, it is necessary to determine the research focus. According to (Creswell, 2010), a study should focus on one phenomenon or one main concept to be explored in detail.

Research focus

The focus of this research is more on developing problems, besides that it serves as a limitation for researchers when conducting research. Thus according to the background, problem formulation and research objectives, the focus of this study is: The process of absorbing community aspirations in development planning in Gorontalo District.

Research Sites and Sites

In this study, the authors took a location in Gorontalo district, namely the Regional Development Planning Agency for Jalan dutulanaa no 2 Limboto-Gorontalo, then in other related fields involved in the Preparation, Evaluation, & Control of Programs, Villages / Districts, as well as related RGOF. The determination of Gorontalo District as the research location is based on the following considerations:

A. Data source

Referring to the view (Maleong, 2000) 4 which explains that according to the selected data source, the types of data in qualitative research are divided into informants, documents and perristiwa. Based on these opinions, this study uses words and actions as well as relevant writing materials as primary data which is taken through interview and observation techniques as well as secondary data based on documentation. Overall, the main data sources for this dissertation research are all stakeholders who are directly involved in the process of absorbing community aspirations in development programs. In this regard, the main data sources for this study were obtained through.

B. Informant

The source of data in this study were informants,. Informants are people who actively provide information about the situation and background conditions as well as research problems. Initially, the informants were selected purposively (purposive), that is, people who are considered to know about the problem of this research are selected, then by Snow Ball until they reach the saturated level (saturation level). again different information). After entering the research field, the researcher contacts certain informants to ask for information, then will continue to expand to other informants who are related to the research focus until complete data and information are obtained and indicate the level of information saturation.

C. Document

This study also uses supporting data that comes from documents, namely notes related to research problems, including the documents used in this study are newspapers, LONG TERM DEVELOPMENT PLANGorontalo Regency and Musreimbang Results reports. regional development planning documents (Regional LONG TERM DEVELOPMENT PLAN, Regional Regional Medium Term Development Plan, LOCAL GOVERNMENT WORK PLANS, RGOFThe Strategic Plan and RGOFWork Plan), REGIONAL EXPENDITURE BUDGER, Technical Guidelines for Implementation of Development Planning Deliberations (DPD) and Regional Government Organization Forum (RGOF), minutes of village development planning deliberations, sub-district development planning deliberations In addition, researchers also made direct observations in the field, namely in the Gorontalo District, the location where the Village Development Planning Consultation was held.

D. Event

At this stage, it requires a process of identification, collection of related data and studying the phenomena associated with the process of absorbing community aspirations in development programs in Gorontalo District. Through this observation, it is also found that there is a process of implementing community

consultation that reflects community participation in formulating community suggestions for development programs.

E. Data Collection Techniques

At the stage of being in the research location, the researcher tries to build trust by making an approach to fostering a close personal relationship with the informants who are the object of the research. In this process the researcher tries to obtain complete information and capture the essence of the information obtained. The researcher uses three kinds of techniques, namely: Observation, Interview, Documentation.

F. Data Validity

To test the validity of the data, this researcher referred to the four criteria found by Lincoln and Guba in (Lincoln, 2002) 5, namely the standard of trust, the standard of transition, the standard dependency, and certainty standards.

G. Credibility

This is to meet the criteria that the data and information collected must contain truth values, which means that the results of qualitative research must be trusted by critical readers and can be accepted by informants who have provided information during the research.

H. Dependability

This criterion is used to assess whether the research process is of good quality or not by seeing whether the research was carried out carefully or not. (1). conceptualizing research plans, (2). collecting data, and (3). interpreting data or informants that have been collected in a study in a research report.

I. Confirmability

This criterion is used to assess whether the research results are of good quality or not. The results of this study, after being triangulated, commented on by the informants and also through the process of sharing, discussions with peers, and the companion team while on the research arena, the next action was for the researcher to report the results of the research in detail and carefully with reference to the focus of the research. This is done in order to meet the transformability and confirmability criteria so that the research report can fulfill the principles of truth, value, consistency and neutrality.

J. Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis is the search or tracking of patterns. Meanwhile, qualitative data analysis is a systematic test of something to determine its parts, the relationship between studies and its relationship to the whole. In practice, data collection and data analysis techniques are not easily separated. The two activities run simultaneously. This means that data analysis should be done simultaneously with data collection and then proceed after data collection is complete. At this stage, the researcher performs the process of deciphering the data according to its parts and examining the parts themselves and the relationships between the parts to obtain a precise understanding and understanding of the overall meaning. In this study, qualitative data analysis was used with the steps of an interactive model of analysis as developed by Miles, Huberman & Saldana with the following procedures: Data condensation, data presentation, drawing conclusions or verification.

K. Data collection

According to (Miles, Huberman and Saldana, 2014) 6 that the data collection process in the field in qualitative research consists of three stages, namely anticipatory data collection, during data collection and post data collection. The following is the data collection stage in the description below: 1). First, Anticipatory data collection, 2) During data collection (During Data Collection), 3). post data collection (post data collection).

L. Draw Conclusions & verification

In drawing conclusions, the researcher concludes from the data that has been described in the presentation of the data. Conclusion in this study is focused. The conclusions that have been drawn from the presentation of the data then become a topic to be discussed and analyzed here, describing conclusions and verification is an attempt to interpret data that has been tested for truth or its validity from the data that has been presented. This qualitative data analysis was carried out continuously, related to data condensation, display, and conclusion / verification respectively as an inseparable analysis. The drawing of conclusions carried out at the data analysis stage carried out is a conclusion to the data presented in the data presentation.

(Miles, Huberman and Saldana, 2014) Collecting data, condensing data, presenting data and drawing conclusions is not something that is linear, but rather an interactive cycle, because it shows a genuine willingness to understand or get a deep, comprehensive, detailed description and understanding of a problem so that can produce a valid conclusion.

Schematically, the data analysis process uses interactive data analysis models Miles, MB and (Hubberman, AM and Saldana, 2014) 8 can be shown in the following chart.

Huberman, AM and Saldana, (2014) Qualitative Data Analysis

The analysis model shows that the four components are interactive, namely mutually influencing and related. First of all, research is carried out in the field by conducting interviews or observations called the data collection stage. Because the data, data presentation collection, data reduction, conclusions or interpretation of the data collected are many, data reduction is held. After the reduction, the data presentation is then held, besides that data collection is also used for data presentation. If these three things are done, a decision or verification is taken. After the data from the field has been collected using the data collection method above, the researcher will process and analyze the data using qualitative analysis without using quantitative techniques.

M. The Process of Absorbing People's Aspirations in Regional Development Planning;

The practice of implementing the Gorontalo District DPD as a means of absorbing the aspirations of the community has provided space for various groups, both from the community, government, and the private sector to be directly involved in submitting their proposals, so that in bringing these elements together, the capacity of the Development Planning Agency is needed to carry out its coordinating function as a bridge. Various elements involved in development planning in order to serve, accommodate, and implement the aspirations of the community in accordance with the program of activities launched. So far, the implementation of the DPD from the lower level in the village / kelurahan, followed by the subdistrict DPD, which is considered to be able to absorb the aspirations of the community from the grassroots, apparently still has many weaknesses

Regional Development and Development Agency itself as a technical planning agency through DPD activities has tried to embrace development actors (stakeholders) to contribute ideas for development in order to absorb aspirations. A high level of involvement indicates that all stakeholders want to take an active role in the participatory planning process as conveyed by the secretary of Regional Development and Development Agency that:

From the results of the documentation, it can be seen that the level of attendance of interested stakeholders is quite high, this can be seen from the level of attendance at the village, sub-district, to district DPD. When viewed from the level of participation that participates in the sub-district DPD in one of the Districts, namely the Tibawa District, based on the researcher's observation that the level of participation of related stakeholders, both from local government officials, vertical agencies to the community plays an active role in participating in the DPD which is held at the sub-district level.

Based on the observations of researchers, the level of presence of stakeholders at msurenbang in tibawa sub-district is 83 participatory consisting of 42 people, 20 RGOF people, 4 Legislative Assembly people, 12 vertical agencies of that number, that the level of participation of related stakeholders, both from local government officials, vertical agencies so that the community plays an active role in participating in the DPD which is held at the sub-district level.

Regional Development and Development Agency's efforts to involve stakeholders should be done, it's just that a high level of stakeholder presence does not guarantee that people's aspirations can be properly absorbed, because the implementation of DPD is still considered by the community to not reflect participatory development planning where proposals are still dominated by parties. which has an influence on government decisions or policies so that community participation in DPD feels empty or meaningless.

From the interview excerpt above, it indicates that elite domination makes unequal relations between the strong and the relatively weaker parties. This is why the crucial issues raised by the community are often ignored, the priorities made sometimes only touch the needs of a few villages so that it is difficult to equalize development, which in the end the community proposals that have been produced through DPD in each village are not well absorbed or included in the list of programs to be discussed at the next sub-district DPD stage.

When the researcher made observations in the field related to the above problems, the researcher found that elite and individual domination almost occurred at every stage of the DPD, this condition was due to the lack of the facilitator's ability to guide DPD activities well. Facilitators who were appointed by Regional Development and Development Agency or from the sub-district at the time of the DPD were not able to encourage community aspirations due to their inability to present ideas and explore community aspirations.

From the results of the DPD when confirmed from various informants. whether all the community proposals through the DPD proposal can be properly accommodated in the discussion of program priorities to be submitted at the DPDkab. However, from the observations of researchers in the field, it seems that many proposals from most villages are not well accommodated, including from the village of Molawahu which is in the tibawa sub-district as described above, even though these proposals are proposed almost every year, many of them are still raw at the discussion stage. The community considers that the implementation of the DPD forum only tends to comply with normative rules, or the DPD forum is only to fulfill the vision and mission of the elected regional head and agree on the district government's priority scale proposals as determined.

The suggestions attached above the researchers show that the proposals from the priority of the Tibawa sub-district head still dominate the priority of the proposals, this is in line with what researchers found when interviewing various informants that the release of the Head of Subdistrict in selecting and determining proposals led to the emergence of various program proposals at the sub-district development planning meetings. which is not the result of the village proposal, thus making the participation that has been netted in the village development planning meeting pointless and not being used properly, this is the case in several sub-districts in Gorontalo District. This indicates that the priority of the Head of Subdistrict is still very strong.

The problems that do exist do not appear to only arise during the implementation of the sub-district DPD, but other problems also arise when the district DPD takes place. Where the results of the DPD have not been implemented properly due to the lack of "commitment" of some RGOFs to the results of the DPD, so there are still RGOF's that propose activities that are not included in the DPD results for various reasons.

So far, the implementation of DPD has often been a battle between the elites, both from the executive and legislative branches. The strength of the two institutions makes the central role that Regional Development and Development Agency has in implementing DPD is only functioned as a deterrent, political intervention from the two institutions has limited the space for Regional Development and Development Agency to synergize and synchronize the aspirations of the community, so that the practice of DPD that has been running so far has always been dominated. So far, the form of interaction carried out by the executive and legislative in accommodating the interests of the community has been in a weak position due to discrimination, so that the process does not prioritize the proposed proposals.

Even though Regional Development and Development Agency has very limited space to absorb aspirations, as a form of Regional Development and Development Agency's responsibility to the community to absorb the aspirations, when before the DPD, Gorontalo District Regional Development and Development Agency itself always takes advantage of Focus Group Discussion activities and other online aspiration services through applications that have been provided by Regional Development and Development Agency as a supporting media in absorb the aspirations, which are then the results of the aspirations which are subsequently under the Ministry of Development and Development.

Starting from the various data mentioned above, both obtained through interviews and observation with participants, and existing documents, it can be concluded that the Regional Development Planning Agency as the sole coordinator has an important task in implementing DPD which is expected to be able to absorb community aspirations from the grassroots. In fact, there are still many weaknesses, where the program proposals produced through the DPD channel have not been able to fulfill the common desire, because at the time of the implementation of the DPD, there is still a lot of domination by the aspirations of those who have influence on the decision, so that community participation in the DPD feels empty. or without meaning. so that the implementation of DPD runs well and becomes an important medium in absorbing the aspirations of the community.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusions are compiled from the presentation of the research results and their discussion. The main conclusions presented are an explanation of the research focus that has been determined previously.

The process of absorbing community aspirations in development planning is very dependent on the ability of Gorontalo District Regional Development and Development Agency as the technical implementer of development planning carried out through the stages of implementing DPD, the process of receiving technical aspirations, and facilitating community aspirations in the decision-making process. Regional Development and Development Agency as the sole coordinator who has an important task in implementing DPD, which is expected to be able to absorb the aspirations of the community from grass roots, there are still many weaknesses. The ability of Regional Development and Development Agency to facilitate and integrate program proposals produced through the DPD channel has not yet fulfilled the common desire, so the implementation of the DPD has not been able to solve the problems faced by the community. The form of Regional Development and Development Agency's effort in managing community aspirations which is prepared to be brought under during the implementation of the DPD has been carried out through the process of receiving community aspirations technically. The mechanism for receiving community aspirations by Regional Development and Development Agency is one of the ways Regional Development and Development Agency can improve the quality of development planning. It's just that the process of receiving community aspirations carried out by Regional Development and Development Agency is not accompanied by an in-depth study of the aspirations so that it does not have an impact on the absorption of community aspirations. This condition makes Regional Development and Development Agency's acceptance of aspirations in the weakest position, because it is done only to fulfill their duties as an organizer, which in turn confirms Regional Development and Development Agency as an aspiration gathering officer.

SUGGESTION

In the process of absorbing aspirations in development planning, the implementation of DPD should be made into an important agenda by the government in absorbing the aspirations of the community, and hopes that Regional Development and Development Agency will continue to improve the technical quality of planning so that Regional Development and Development Agency needs to implement policies that are binding on stakeholders to be able to accommodate priority proposals from the community. This policy must be implemented so that the aspirations are not only owned by influential people who only give priority to groups and individuals, but rather prioritize community proposals. For this reason, Regional Development and Development Agency is expected to always emphasize stakeholders so that whenever they convey their aspirations at the DPD they still uphold the principles of deliberation including the principle of anti-dominance, so that decisions can run in balance, therefore all stakeholders should be able to eliminate sectoral egos, power egos, personal egos in the decision-making process so that development in Gorontalo district in the future truly reflects pro-poor development so that the social welfare of society can be realized. Likewise for the Gorontalo district Regional Development and Development Agency, which is responsible for the development planning process, to be more pro-active in carrying out its duties and functions as regional development coordinator, be it technical, analytical, administrative and communication. personal ego in the decision-making process so that development in Gorontalo district in the future truly reflects pro-poor development so that the social welfare of the community can be realized. Likewise for the Gorontalo district Regional Development and Development Agency, which is responsible for the development planning process, to be more pro-active in carrying out its duties and functions as regional development coordinator, be it technical, analytical, administrative and communication. personal ego in the decision-making process so that development in Gorontalo district in the future truly reflects pro-poor development so that the social welfare of the community can be realized. Likewise for the Gorontalo district Regional Development and Development Agency, which is responsible for the development planning process, to be more pro-active in carrying out its duties and functions as regional development coordinator, be it technical, analytical, administrative and communication.

The government should keep prioritizing priority activities to be accommodated, the priority of the program is not only in the infrastructure sector, but the economic and social sectors cannot be overlooked. To meet the needs of society in all fields, accommodating programs should support one another, including infrastructure, the economy, and the social sector, which are expected to have a reciprocal relationship. For this reason, the Gorontalo District government should select and sort out program proposals that are considered urgent so that they can be made priorities, because the sources of funding or budget that are owned are very limited, then with a good distribution it will have an impact on the welfare of the community and will not cause budget waste.

Theoretical Suggestions

Regional Development and Development Agency's efforts to absorb community aspirations which place more emphasis on procedural aspects, or view a series of planning stages as a process that must be carried out to absorb the aspirations of the community, Regional Development and Development Agency will inevitably be faced with significant challenges, a long process and the many parties involved often lead to planning becomes ineffective. Likewise, if you look at the issue of community aspirations lying on the inability of planners, it will have an impact on the quality of planning. This is as stated (Faludi, 1973) 9 that there are two theories in planning that can be used in regional development planning, namely procedural and substantive theories. In procedural planning theory it is considered a series of procedures to achieve goals in planning. there is a logical sequence of planning that must be followed to produce a plan. Meanwhile, substantive tends to look at the root of the problem at hand. Therefore, procedural theory should have a larger portion in carrying out its function. Meanwhile, substantive theory supports procedural theory. But in reality, substantive theory plays a bigger role through analytical methods that are absorbed by procedural theory. Therefore, in practice, it should not be separated between the two, it is hoped that it will form an elaboration to become an effective plan. Therefore, procedural theory should have a larger portion in carrying out its function. Meanwhile, substantive theory supports procedural theory. But in reality, substantive theory plays a bigger role through analytical methods that are absorbed by procedural theory. Therefore, in practice, it should not be separated between the two, it is hoped that it will form an elaboration to become an effective plan. Therefore, procedural theory should have a larger portion in carrying out its function. Meanwhile, substantive theory supports procedural theory. But in reality, substantive theory plays a bigger role through analytical methods that are absorbed by procedural theory. Therefore, in practice, it should not be separated between the two, it is hoped that it will form an elaboration to become an effective plan.

One way to maintain the quality of planning is the need for the contribution of a stakeholder to convey concern and concern in the form of aspirations, (Berman, 2017) 10 requires that aspirations conveyed through deliberation be carried out in a dialogical manner because deliberation can actually gather many people to reach a mutual agreement. provided that they adhere to the principle of dialogue, the principle of partiality, the principle of anti-domination, and the principle of anti-discrimination. What is conveyed by Berman is considered as one of the rights for all people who are considered capable of influencing policy. This was then emphasized by (Sjafrizal, 2014) 11 that the development planning process must create a public space as a forum for participation,

From what has been explained above that the planning process has its own mechanism in terms of its implementation, in the context of regional development technically Gorontalo District Regional Development and Development Agency is trusted by the regional government in carrying out the technical formulation process of development planning. Regarding what was stated (Berman, 2017) 12 and (Sjafrizal, 2014) 13 the ability of Regional Development and Development Agency is very important as a determinant of whether the development planning process is good or not, especially in absorbing community aspirations. Currently, the trigger for not properly absorbing community aspirations lies in the ability of Regional Development and Development Agency officials to translate problems, identify problems and communicate with the community is not optimal.

Based on the problems often faced by Regional Development and Development Agency, the readiness of the apparatus is very important to provide service satisfaction to the community according to (Saleh et al. 2013) 14 one indicator that can be used to see the quality of services provided by the government is participation, that the provision of public services must be able to encourage the emergence of positive community participation in the delivery of public services by taking into account the aspirations, needs and expectations of the wider community. Meanwhile, in terms of the ability of the apparatus, (Saleh et al. 2013) 15 has emphasized that an apparatus who has credibility is not only capable of providing services to the community but an apparatus must have technical, administrative, communication, and technical proficiency or skills. analytic.

A number of rational reasons are stated (Saleh et al., 2013) 16 above that in fact technical, administrative, communication and analytical skills are the supporting personal potentials needed by an apparatus as a civil servant officer, because the apparatus has an intensive interactive relationship with the community. This clearly has a very strong relevance to the practice of regional development planning, because in fact the skills and skills of these officials are needed to bridge the process of coordination and mediation between stakeholders in formulating development programs. so that the problem of not optimizing the contribution of the apparatus to the planning process is allegedly the result of the placement of the apparatus which is not yet in accordance with their skills and proficiency.

The problem of not being properly absorbed by the people's aspirations does not only come from technical problems, but other problems arise from the implementation of development activities including the implementation of DPD. The strong dominance of the executive and legislative elites in determining programs to make development planning based on political elements, the position of the community is only involved in

the program planning stage, but in the process of determining the results of decisions about which programs to be approved by the community are not given the opportunity, which in the end political pressure cannot be released from the development planning process. Under these circumstances, many of the programs produced are not decisions made in the DPD but are entrusted programs from certain groups that try to take advantage of the development planning process. Regional Development and Development Agency as a technical institution can not do much karma is still under the political pressure of the authorities, this is because the structure and work procedures are still under the shadow of the Regent so that every action is based on orders from the regent, therefore these problems make people's aspirations slow to be absorbed or not absorbed at all.

Related to the above, development planning from a political aspect (Dye, 1992) 17 gives his view that politics is about who gets scarce government resources, where, when, why, and how, this explains that in practice public policy is formulated as authority consisting of seniors, supreme heads, executives, legislators, administrators, advisors, kings, and so on. Those who are authorized in this political system are responsible for a particular problem where at one point they are asked to make decisions at a later date, what Dye said should be in making decisions involving interested parties,

Likewise, according to (Faludi, 1972) 18 suggests that in making decisions on development programs requires collaboration between groups of people, politicians and planners who support each other. the authorities so that their wishes are accommodated, namely the community, community leaders and community organizations, then politicians are elected representatives whose aim is to influence decisions, namely the legislative elements that are representatives of the LEGISLATIVE ASSEMBLY and the executive, namely the local government and the agencies they supervise, while the planners act as technical executors under the direct protection of the Agency. regional development planning.

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